

NON-VERBAL COMMUNICATION IN DISTANCE LEARNING

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***Annotation.** This work is dedicated to the analysis and discussion of issues pertaining to the processing of nonverbal signals in the context of online communication. This study explores the role of emojis, smileys, and other graphic elements in online communication, as well as the influence of organizational culture on the perception of emotions in email correspondence.*

***Keywords:** processing of nonverbal signals, online communication, email correspondence, nonverbal information, emojis, smiley, interpersonal interaction.*

With the rise of social media, messaging apps, and video conferencing tools, people increasingly rely on technology to communicate with others. However, unlike face-to-face communication, online communication lacks physical presence and nonverbal cues that are critical in conveying emotions, attitudes, and intentions. As a result, processing nonverbal cues in online communication has become a complex task that requires careful attention and interpretation.

Darinskaya L.A., Molodtsova G.I., using content analysis, analyzed psychological and pedagogical publications considering issues of non-verbal communication in online learning. It turned out that non-verbal communication in distance learning plays an important role, as it helps to establish and maintain contact between the teacher and the student. Gestures, facial expressions, intonation and other non-verbal means of communication help to create an atmosphere of trust and understanding between the participants in the learning process. They also contribute to improving the perception, memorization of educational material, help to avoid misunderstandings and conflicts. They note that although non-verbal communication plays an important role in distance learning, there are practically no specific methods for its implementation in online education. [2]

Borodulina N.Yu., Makeeva M.N., Ilyina I.E. by using the descriptive method, examined the role of non-verbal communication in online foreign language learning. The study showed that non-verbal means of communication, such as gestures and facial expressions, play an important role in the learning process. They help create a sense of presence and involve students in communication processes. They also

contribute to better memorization of new vocabulary and increased motivation of students. [1]

Feng Yu describes a study on the use of non-verbal communication in online learning. Non-verbal cues such as eye contact, gestures, facial expressions, and posture can help in understanding the emotional state of learners. The study emphasizes the importance of correctly interpreting non-verbal cues to improve the learning process. It is also mentioned that non-verbal communication takes up a larger part of overall communication than verbal communication. [3]

Real J. A., Carandang M. A. D., Contreras A. G. L., & Diokno P. C. J. investigated the use of non-verbal language among students. A quantitative descriptive analysis method was used to collect data through questionnaires. The respondents were 287 secondary school students in Doha, Qatar. Percentage and weight means were used to analyze the data. The results show that the most frequently used non-verbal communications are gestures and body posture. Thus, if students often sit with hunched backs and bowed heads, this can be perceived as a sign of insecurity or lack of interest. And if they use various gestures, including lifting a leg, this is perceived as an inability to concentrate or lack of interest. At the same time, it is mentioned that non-verbal communication can lead to misunderstandings and incorrect perception of information in online communication. [7]

As described above, processing nonverbal cues in online communication is a complex task that requires careful attention and interpretation. Without the visual and auditory information that is present in face-to-face communication, people may have difficulty accurately interpreting the emotions and intent behind messages. However, it is possible to improve your understanding and interpretation of messages in online communication by using some strategies.

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